

The Effects of Signal Level of the Microwave Generator on the Brillouin Gain Spectrum in BOTDA and BOTDR

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Abstract—In this study, Brillouin Gain Spectrum (BGS) is experimentally analyzed in the Brillouin Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (BOTDR) and Brillouin Optical Time Domain Analyzer (BOTDA). For this purpose, the signal level of the microwave generator is varied and the effects of BGS are investigated. In the setups, 20 km conventional single mode fiber is used to both setups and laser wavelengths are selected around 1550 nm. To achieve best results, it can be used between 5 dBm to 15 dBm signal level of microwave generator for BOTDA and BOTDR setups.

Keywords—Microwave signal level, Brillouin gain spectrum, BOTDA, BOTDR.

I. INTRODUCTION

OPTICAL fibers have been used in many different applications. The most known application is in the area of telecommunications [1]. Optical fibers have been utilized not only in the telecommunications but also common in fiber sensor systems. There are a lot of application areas of the fiber sensors such as medical, security, chemical, military, environmental etc. Different physical quantities can be measured such as temperature, strain, vibrations, pressure, speed, distance, gases, etc. by fiber optic sensors [2]-[17].

Recently, distributed fiber optic sensors aiming security are very popular. They make use of back scatterings in fiber optic cable. The best-known back scatterings in the fiber are Rayleigh scattering that has an elastic effect; the Brillouin and the Raman scatterings that belong to the inelastic effect [1].

In this paper, stimulated Brillouin based distributed fiber optic sensors are analyzed by using two techniques, which are BOTDA and BOTDR. When the input signal power exceeds the threshold in a single mode fiber (SMF), Stimulated Brillouin Scattering (SBS) that is a nonlinear optical process occurs. Various fundamental and applied aspects of SBS were studied and a great deal of papers is published recently about

the researches that belong to SBS. The details of the SBS can be found in [7]-[12].

II. THEORY OF THE BRILLOUIN SCATTERING

In the Brillouin scattering theory, the process of scattering can be defined as the nonlinear effect between light and acoustic wave and this scattering can be spontaneous or stimulated. When an oscillating electric field at the pump frequency known as f_p , then the electrostriction process produces a macroscopic acoustic wave at the frequency f_B , where f_B is the Stokes shift. In the spontaneous Brillouin scattering, pump photons are suppressed. This results in creation of Stokes photon and an acoustic phonon concurrently. The energy conservation and momentum conservation (MC) must be followed in similar scattering processes [18]-[21].

For conservation of energy, f_B is close to equal to $f_p - f_s$, where f_s is frequency of stokes wave. MC needed is $k_A = k_p - k_s$ difference, where k_A , k_p and k_s are momentum vectors of acoustic, pump and Stokes waves respectively.

When v_A is acoustic velocity, and then dispersion relation can be written with (1), (2) [18];

$$f_B = v_A + |\vec{k}_A| = v_A |\vec{k}_p - \vec{k}_s| \quad (1)$$

$$f_B = 2 v_A |\vec{k}_p| \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (2)$$

In (1) and (2), θ is the angle between k_p and k_s and they are taken nearly equal. The frequency shift depends on θ . If $\theta=0^\circ$, frequency shift (FS) is also equal to zero and FS only can be seen backward direction. If $\theta=\pi$, FS is maximum at backward direction. If the maximum backward shift given with Brillouin FS $v_B = f_B/2\pi$ formula, from (1) and (2) [18];

$$|\vec{k}_p| = 2\pi n/\lambda_p \quad (3)$$

will be calculated with this definition. Where, n is reflective index of SMF, λ_p is pump wavelength. Consequently, SBS can transfer all power from the pump to the scattered wave [20]-[21].

For stationary conditions, SBS can be described by (4), (5). For simplification, $f_p \cong f_s$ and $\alpha_p \cong \alpha_s$ can be accepted. Wave Equations can be written;

$$\frac{\partial I_s}{\partial z} = -g_B I_s I_p + \alpha_s I_s \quad (4)$$

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$$\frac{\partial I_P}{\partial z} = -g_B I_S I_P - \alpha_P I_P \quad (5)$$

In (4) and (5), I_S and I_P are the light intensity of signal and pump light respectively, α_S and α_P are the fiber attenuation, g_B is the Brillouin gain coefficient of the fiber.

For the Brillouin threshold estimating, pump depletion can be neglected. Using $I_P(z) = I_P(0) e^{-\alpha z}$ and integrating it over fiber length L , (6) can be written as [19], [20];

$$I_S(0) = I_S(L) \exp(g_B P_0 L_{\text{eff}} / A_{\text{eff}} - \alpha L) \quad (6)$$

when $P_0 = I_P(0) A_{\text{eff}}$ is the input pump power, A_{eff} is effective mode area and L_{eff} is the effective fiber length of fiber considering fiber loss and fiber absorbability, then (7) can be written;

$$L_{\text{eff}} = \frac{1}{\alpha} [1 - \exp(-\alpha L)] \quad (7)$$

Equation (8) shows how a Stokes signal incident at $z=L$ grows in the backward direction because of Brillouin amplification occurring as a result of SBS. The peak value of the Brillouin gain is given by;

$$g_B(\Delta f) = g_0 \frac{\gamma \left(\frac{\Delta f_B}{2}\right)^2}{\Delta f^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta f}{2}\right)^2} \quad (8)$$

where γ is polarization coefficient. Δf_B is the bandwidth of Brillouin gain [18], [19];

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Fig. 1 shows Brillouin optical time domain analyzer (BOTDA) scheme. The input laser signal is applied by the continuous wave (CW) tunable laser source (TLS) that has SANTEC TSL-210V. The wavelength of the laser is around 1550 nm and modulated into microwave (MW) signal generator by using electro-optic modulator (EOM) as the pump of the SBS, and then pulsed input signals are amplified with Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA). After, amplified signals pass through port 1 to port 2 of the optical circulator; the signals propagate along SMF having a length of 20 km. The CW laser signal is launched at the opposite end of the fiber that is called the probe signals. Back-scattered SBS signal is passing through port 2 to port 3 of the optical circulator. Then, SBS signals are amplified by the second EDFA and divide by 3 dB coupler that are being sent to high-resolution optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) and photo diode (PD). Finally, electrical signals at the output of PD are amplified by the radio frequency amplifier (RFA), which is analyzed by the radio frequency spectrum analyzer (RFSA).

Fig. 2 shows Brillouin optical time domain reflectometry (BOTDR) scheme. BOTDR utilizes only pulse laser and laser pulses propagate along single direction of SMF as it can be seen from the Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 2 uses same optical component with Fig. 1 except CW laser source.

Fig. 1 Brillouin optical time domain analyzer (BOTDA) experimental setup

Fig. 2 Brillouin optical time domain reflectometry (BOTDR) experimental setup

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Firstly, BOTDA that is shown in Fig. 1 is analyzed. MW signal generator modulates the CW laser signal and, it propagates through SMF, and power level of the MW signal is varied between -20 dBm to +20 dBm. Fig. 3 shows BGS for various signal levels. It can be observed from the Fig. 3 that the Brillouin scattering increased by increasing the power level of MW generator, however different result is obtained at the +20 dBm signal level. At this signal level, BGS peak power is lower than +15 dBm because of the Stokes line that reaches the saturation power level.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3 Brillouin gain spectra for the different signal levels for BOTDA setup (a) +15 dBm, (b) 0 dBm, (c) -10 dBm

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4 Optical spectrums for the different signal levels for BOTDA setup (a) +15 dBm, (b) 0 dBm, (c) -10 dBm

The optical spectrums of the same MW signal levels are shown in Fig. 4. Frequency difference between two lasers is adjusted about the Brillouin back scattering frequency, which is around 10.85 GHz, with the use of TLS. First peak is pump, second peak is probe and, third peak is the harmonic of the MW generator.

Secondly, BOTDR that is shown in Fig. 2 is analyzed. For this purpose, same procedure is followed with BOTDA. BGS for the various signal levels is shown in Fig. 5. It can be observed that Brillouin scattering increased by increasing the power level of MW generator.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5 Brillouin gain spectrums for the different signal levels for BOTDR setup (a) +15 dBm, (b) 0 dBm, (c) -10 dBm

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 6 Optical spectrums for the different signal levels for BOTDR setup (a) +15 dBm, (b) 0 dBm, (c) -10 dBm

The optical spectrum of the same MW signal levels are shown in Fig. 6 for BOTDR. The first peak is pump and the second peak is Brillouin back-scattering signal.

Fig. 7 shows the variations of BGS peak power for various

MW signal levels. BOTDA and BOTDR setups have the same properties except +20 dBm level for BOTDA setup.

Fig. 7 The variations of BGS peak power versus MW signal levels

V. CONCLUSION

Many variable parameters on BOTDA and BOTDR setups can be observed. BGS peaks are analyzed by varying the MW signal levels. The BGS of the BOTDR is proportional to the varied MW signal level. This response is also similar for BOTDA setup. However, BOTDA setup shows a nonlinear change for +20 dBm MW signal level. Finally, BOTDA and BOTDR setups can be used between 5 dBm to 15 dBm for best results.

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